

SOLUTIONS TO PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS IN YOUNG JUDOISTS

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Annotation: At present, problems related to increasing the psychological readiness of athletes remain relevant, since it is much easier to achieve a certain level of physical and technical-tactical readiness for a tournament or competition than mental readiness. The mental state of an athlete is a determining factor in successful performance before and during competition. Often the reason for unsuccessful performance at competitions is the presence of psychological barriers among athletes that prevent them from developing combat readiness for competition.

Key words: psychological preparation of judokas, psychological barriers, taking into account factors typical for this group.

Introduction. Judo is one of the most common types of combat sports [3]. The competitiveness of judo wrestling has a progressive trend. The level of qualifications of athletes at major tournaments makes it necessary to improve the applied methods, not so much of versatile general and special physical preparedness, but of the psychological preparation of judoists [1, 4, 7]. Wrestlers compete under strong mental stress, which is specific to any martial arts. The use of permitted painful holds makes Sambo especially spectacular, but at the same time it places special demands on a number of mental qualities and states of a judoka [2, 3, 5].

A systematic description of the human psyche allows us to fill the concept with content: psychological preparation of judokas. Typically, in martial arts, “motor” sports, the goal of psychological preparation is to achieve the required level of mental arousal (combat form) by the time of competition [8, 11, 12]. In sports

with complex coordination of movements, in the process of psychological preparation, ideomotor “playing out” of the movement program is carried out [9, 10, 14]. For many coaches, psychological preparation often comes down to “pressure” (must, must, don’t let me down). Psychological preparation in judo is a systemic process in which all developed psychological qualities are interconnected [15, 16]. The psychological preparedness of a judoka depends on the degree of development of specialized perceptions: a sense of distance and timing of a throw, orientation on the tatami, reaction speed, the ability to predict the actions of an opponent, tactical thinking, attention, which is often determined by his mental state.

The state of mental readiness does not arise spontaneously. It is formed and consolidated in the process of educating and training athletes, in the presence of targeted psychological preparation for each specific competition [17, 18].

Processing the results of the survey allowed us to formulate recommendations for coaches on organizing the psychological preparation of judokas for competitions, taking into account factors typical for this group in overcoming psychological barriers.

1. Overcoming fear of the enemy caused by:

a) lack of information about the opponent: providing athletes with information about opponents: joint viewing of video recordings of fights with the participation of opponents; stories about the fights of those athletes who met with these opponents at competitions;

b) exaggerating the opponent’s merits: organizing critical reflection by athletes of the information received: analysis of the opponents’ technical and tactical techniques, highlighting his strengths and weaknesses, strategic planning of response actions;

c) underestimating one’s own capabilities: organizing the reflexive activities of athletes: watching video recordings of fights with one’s own participation, analyzing one’s own technical and tactical actions; identifying your own strengths, which can become a “counterbalance” to the opponent’s strengths or allow you to take

advantage of his weaknesses; identifying mistakes and successful techniques, planning “work on mistakes”;

d) getting to know the opponent, knowing his strengths: organizing athletes’ understanding of the competitive tasks facing them related to countering the strengths and technical and tactical techniques of their opponents.

The method common to the four factors is the organization of training fights, in which one of the participants acts as a potential opponent, fighting in accordance with the identified characteristics of a given athlete, and the second builds a fight taking into account the strengths and weaknesses of the opponent.

2. Overcoming the fear of losing caused by:

a) fear of condemnation by the team, coach:

– creating a friendly sports team: organizing joint recreation, holding conversations about friendship and mutual assistance, support in the team, using methods of reward not only for individual, but also for team successes;

– moral support for the trainer of athletes: encouragement, calming, setting for a gradual increase in sportsmanship, active participation in planning battle tactics;

b) fear of being worse than other athletes, of being disappointed in oneself:

– organization of reflective trainings for athletes, including analysis of their own competitive activity, technical and tactical techniques, strengths and weaknesses, as well as planning ways to overcome shortcomings in the level of preparedness;

– organizing self-confidence training, which involves practicing facial expressions, gestures, words, behavior and actions characteristic of self-confident people (athletes);

c) fear of letting the team and coach down, not participating in important competitions:

- organizing athletes’ awareness of the essence and features of the tasks of the upcoming competitions, related exclusively to technical and tactical actions, the strategy of the fight, while consciously distracting athletes from “soul-searching”;

conducting trainings on motivation for success with leveling manifestations of motivation to avoid failures;

d) heightened pride, fear of showing results lower than before:

– holding conversations about the fact that in sports, while striving for victory, one should be aware of the possibility of losing, inviting famous highly qualified athletes to these conversations;

– playing out simulated situations of losing a fight with an analysis of possible causes and consequences, with “playing out” words, gestures, facial expressions of the loser, team and coaches, with planning methods

psychological support for the athlete.

Methods of psychological preparation for competitions common to all factors:

– training athletes in self-control of neuro-emotional stress, performance and state of the neuromuscular system: assessing their condition according to the parameters of performance and neuro-emotional stress, based on correct self-assessment, prepare for training and performance in competitions;

– training athletes in the skills of voluntary relaxation and mobilization: theoretical studies, analysis of errors and the search for ways to eliminate or correct them based on self-regulation.

3. Overcoming the fear of not being able to withstand the high pace of combat caused by:

a) lack of self-confidence:

- organization of reflexive activity of athletes: viewing video recordings of fights with one’s own participation, analysis of one’s own technical and tactical actions;

- organization of reflective trainings for athletes, including analysis of their own competitive activity, technical and tactical techniques, strengths and weaknesses, as well as planning ways to overcome shortcomings in the level of preparedness;

- organization of self-confidence trainings, which involve practicing facial expressions, gestures, words, behavior and actions characteristic of self-confident people (athletes);

b) insufficient physical fitness:

- organization of testing of general physical fitness of athletes, joint analysis of test results;
- organization of reflexive activity of athletes aimed at analyzing their own shortcomings in physical fitness and planning ways to overcome them;

c) poor psychological well-being, including those caused by recent injuries and fear of their recurrence:

- training athletes in self-control of neuro-emotional stress, performance and the state of the neuromuscular system: assessing their condition according to the parameters of performance and neuro-emotional stress, based on correct self-assessment, prepare for training and competitions;
- training athletes in the skills of voluntary relaxation and mobilization: theoretical classes (information about the psychophysiological meaning of the formed states, the mechanisms of occurrence of certain sensations), analysis of errors and study of developments, options for eliminating them using means of self-regulation.

Conclusions. 1. An important component of the sports training of judokas is psychological preparation, the importance of which is especially high when preparing for competitions. The success of competitive wrestling is influenced by many factors, which include the so-called psychological barriers: fear of the opponent, fear of losing, fear of not being able to withstand the high pace of the fight, fear of losing the fight, fear of injury and fear of unfair refereeing. Psychological barriers can arise for various reasons, the nature of which determines the factors for overcoming barriers and the methods of psychological preparation of wrestlers for competitions.

2. Typical reasons for the emergence of psychological barriers characteristic of young judokas, regardless of sports qualifications and competitive experience, are the following:

- fear of the enemy: insufficient or inadequate information about the enemy;

- fear of losing: fear of showing worse results than before and being disappointed in yourself;

- fear of not being able to withstand the high pace of the fight: lack of self-confidence and insufficient physical preparedness.

3. The author's recommendations for overcoming psychological barriers in young judokas can reduce anxiety and increase the athlete's psycho-emotional readiness for competition.

References:

1. Ustoev, A. K., & Babarahmatov, B. B. (2020). Спорт ўйинларининг ташкилий асосларида кўп йиллик тайёрлов тизими. *Молодой ученый*, (21), 799-801.
2. Ustoev, A. K. (2021). Development of speed-power abilities in young sambists. *Current research journal of pedagogics*, 2(11), 157-160.
3. Устоев, А. К. (2022). Формирование волевых усилий у подростков в процессе занятий физическим воспитанием. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(1), 14-18.
4. Kurbanovich, U. A. (2022). Ways to Solving Problems in Training Young Kurash Wrestlers. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(9), 108-111.
5. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2020). Ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда иродавий сифатларни жисмоний тарбия воситалари орқали ривожлантириш. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (9 (94)), 56-62.
6. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Юлдашевич, Т. Д. (2020). Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 24 (76), pp. 36-38). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості.
7. Alikulovich, M. K., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 8(3), 2021.

8. Alikulovich, M. K. (2022, October). The significance of psychological preparation of young swimmers. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 84-88).

9. Alikulovich, M. K. (2022). Mobile Games on the Water as a Means of Developing the Physical Qualities of School Children. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 783-786.

10. Maxkamovich, A. Y., & Abdukahorovich, S. K. (2019). Modern approaches to the content of physical education of schoolchildren in the continuing education system. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 7(12).

11. Mahkamovich, A. Y. (2022). Technology of using outdoor games in the development of physical qualities of junior schoolchildren. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(4), 1-5.

12. Менгликулов, Х. (2023). Harakatli o'yinlar orqali 14-15 yoshli suzuvchilarning jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirish. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(3), 230-236.

13. Менгликулов, Х. А. (2022). Ёш сузувчиларни ўргатишнинг бошланғич bosqichida танловнинг назарий жиҳатлари. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (8 (117)), 55-59.

14. Турдимуродов, Д. (2023). Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida qat'iyatlilik sifatini jismoniy tarbiya darslarida tarbiyalash. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(3), 218-223.

15. Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldashevich. (2023). Formation and development of volitional regulation in preschool children. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(2), 33–40.

16. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Preschool period: pedagogical aspect of education of will in a child. *Current Research Journal of Pedagogics (2767-3278)*, 2(09), 47-51.

17. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Testing volitional qualities for students of high schools of secondary school. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 405-413.

18. Турдимуродов, Д. (2021). Formation and education of will in schoolchildren in the process of physical education lesson. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(02), 64-74.